

AMIR TEMUR AND THE PERIOD OF THE TEMURIDS.

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Annotation: The article highlights the events of Amir Temur and the Temurid era, which lasted from the late 14th to the early 16th century. The article shows that Under Temur's rule, development of every sphere of the state, including culture, politics, economy. Amir Temur and his descendants made a great contribution to the field of science and art, therefore, it is emphasized that the period of the Temurids is considered an important period in history. Emphasis is placed on the extent to which Amir Temur improved Samarkand after occupying a large area of Central Asia. The descendants of Amir Temur, especially Mirzo Ulug'bek, made a great contribution to the prosperity of the state during the period of the Temurids. Article explores that after the death of Amir Temur, the era of the Temurids ended, but the rich cultural heritage left by them is still preserved.

Key words: Amir Temur, Tamerlane, Temurid empire, Khoja-Ilgar, iron, great lame, Samarkand, golden age of Persian and Islamic art, Mirzo Ulugbek, the Safavid and Ottoman Empires.

Amir Temur, commonly known as Tamerlane, was once an effective ruler and conqueror who founded the Temurid Empire in Central Asia in the 14th century which is stretching from the Mediterranean Sea to India. Amir Temur is one of the figures who has finished greatness and perfection no longer only in the field of centralized kingdom building, governance, military skills, however also in the subject of morality, faith, education. The fantastic commander's respect for his mentors and religious leaders is a clear instance of this.

In this regard, we can cite the moral programs, teachings, advice of Amir Temur, as nicely as a number of historic works created about him. Among them are the world-famous works "Tuzuki Temuriy", "Malfuzoti Temuriy", "Voqioti Temuriy" and "Mujmal-i Fasihiy" by way of the 15th century historian Fasih Ahmad Hawafi, "Zafarnoma" via Nizamiddin Shami and Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi, Ibn Arabshah. Among them are such works as "Ajayib ul-maqdur fi-ahbori Temur", "Temurnoma" by Salohiddin ibn Mullo Aloiddin hoja Eshan (Salohiddin Tashkendi).

Temur Taragay ibn Barlas was born on April 9, 1336 in the small village of Khoja-Ilgar. The identify Temur is translated from Turkic as "iron", which in many respects influenced his strong-willed character and in addition fate. He was once a courageous younger man, his mother and father and mentors raised him as a actual warrior. Despite the wound in the leg that he acquired in battle, he had super power and until the last days he personally participated in all campaigns and battles. Therefore, historians referred to as him the Great Lame.

The foremost intention of Temur was once to overcome the fragmentation of Mawarannahr and to unite these lands into a single state. Despite its origin, he used to be able to oust the Mongols from Mawarannahr and to unite the lands into one giant state.

Under Temur's leadership, the Timurid Empire grew to become one of the greatest and most effective empires in history, stretching from the Middle East to India and Russia. Temur himself used to be a expert military commander and a ruthless chief who used to be recognised for his brutal methods and fierce determination.

During his reign, Temur conquered significant territories, which includes Persia, Iraq, and parts of India. He also constructed awesome cities, such as Samarkand and Herat, which grew to become centers of way of life and learning in the region. He made Samarkand the capital of his empire – a desolate metropolis near the ruins of the ancient capital of Sogdiana – Afrosiab. Here, he soon started out the development of protective walls, the fort and his residence. Under Temur's patronage, Samarkand, the capital of the Timurid Empire, transformed into a spectacular metropolis. Grandiose mosques, madrasas (religious schools), and mausoleums decorated the city, showcasing the extremely good Timurid architectural style with its complex tilework, hovering domes, and towering minarets. Samarkand became a hub of scholarship and creative excellence, attracting renowned astronomers, mathematicians, and poets.

One of the most lasting legacies of the Timurid Empire was its cultural and creative achievements. The length of the Timurids is often referred to as a golden age of Persian and Islamic art, with many significant contributions in the fields of architecture, literature, and music. The period of Timur and the Timurids is an necessary stage in the improvement of science, culture, spirituality, literature and artwork of the East in general, and Central Asia in particular, a new historic period, a turning point.

In particular, kings and princes such as Amir Temur, Mirzo Ulugbek, Boysungur Mirzo, Hussein Boykaro, Babur Mirzo, Timurid princesses strengthened the basis of the Timurid spirituality due to their appreciate for science and enlightenment, and at the price of many constructions, creative work and organizational and financial work performed.

Muhammad Taragay Ulugbek, the grandson of Amir Temur, one of the priceless successors of the Timurid dynasty, who led the course of public administration and enlightenment, is additionally one of the figures who left an indelible mark on world history. During his reign, two beautiful madrassas have been constructed in Samarkand. They taught secular sciences as nicely as spiritual sciences. It is mentioned that he, along with other well-known scholars, taught younger human beings in these madrassas as soon as a week. Later, madrasas were constructed in Bukhara and Gijduvan, Bibikhanim mosque in Samarkand, Amir Temur mausoleum, Shahizinda and Registan complexes had been completed, and caravanserais, tim, chorsu, and baths were built in different cities.

However, Temur's empire started to decline after his death in 1405. After the death of the empire's founder, the empire confronted inner power struggles amongst his descendants. Succession disputes and rivalries between Timur's grandsons and great-grandsons weakened the empire and led to infighting within the ruling family. His successors were now not as capable as he was, and internal strife and external pressures weakened the empire. Incompetent rulers have been unable to successfully govern the empire or tackle the challenges it faced, leading to further interior divisions and decline.

By the 16th century, the Temurid Empire had fragmented into smaller states, and sooner or later fell to the rising electricity of the Safavid and Ottoman Empires. Following these events, the remnants of the Timurid Empire scattered throughout Central Asia, with some participants of the dynasty in search of refuge in India.

In conclusion, while the empire eventually fell apart, the duration of Amir Temur and the Temurids has a distinctive area in the records of Uzbek statehood. During this period, as a end result of the efforts and direct leadership of Amir Temur, science, way of life and structure flourished. Among the Timurids there had been devotees of science, in particular, Mirzo Ulugbek, Bobur Mirzo and many other representatives of a range of spheres who labored for the duration of this period. Amir Temur and the Timurid dynasty left a lasting impact on the records of the location and on the development of Islamic art and culture.

The learn about of the religious heritage of this duration is one of the most pressing tasks of today. After the independence of our country, an goal opinion was expressed about our history, culture, excellent scientists, superb commanders, statesmen, scientific-practical, creative works, conferences had been held, treasured statistics on the records of the duration used to be generalized and received new content.

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